

Journal of Information Management and Library Studies

ISSN 2708-6089

Vol. 8, issue.1, 2025

Date of Acceptance: 14 June, 2025
Date of Publication: 29 June, 2025

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES OF PUNJAB, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of the study is to look into the possibilities for digital transformation in university libraries in Punjab, Pakistan. This study explains that what resources were digitized during the digital transformation, what challenges were faced. **Methodology:** The research methodology for this study was involved a quantitative approach. The investigator gathered data through a structured questionnaire that was prepared on Google Forms. The population of the study is University librarians and the sample size is sixty-nine (n=69) in this study. The purposive sampling technique was employed who were involved in digital resource services. Data was analyzed through SPSS and used descriptive statistics for the interpretation of the results. **Findings:** The findings show that libraries have different types of digitized resources including scanned books, e-books, e-journals, e-reports, e-newspapers, scanned theses/dissertations, and A-V materials. Libraries were using integrated library system, content management system, and institutional repository and were using own servers for hosting services. This study highlighted some key challenges such as copyright/DRM and licensing issues, inadequate funding, user authentication issues, data security and privacy issues. **Originality:** This study helps those libraries who are interested in adoption of digitization and know in advance what difficulties was faced.

Keywords: Digital transformation, University libraries, Libraries, Punjab, Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Digital Transformation (DT) refers to the integration of digital technology into all areas of an organization's operations, resulting in fundamental changes to how the organization operates and delivers value to its customers or users. This involves leveraging technologies such as cloud computing, big data, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things (IoTs) to improve business processes, enhance customer experiences, and drive innovation (Ndou, 2023; Rath et al., 2024).

Digital Transformation has a long and complex history that can be traced back to the development of the first digital computers in the 1950s and 1960s. These early machines paved the way for the automation of manual tasks and the processing of large amounts of data that marking the beginning of a new era of technological advancement. The advent of the personal computer and local area networks (LANs) in the 1970s and 1980s (Makovoz & Lysenko, 2024). The 1990s and 2000s witnessed the emergence of the internet and the World Wide Web (WWW) which created new opportunities for communication, collaboration, and commerce. This was the era of the increased focus on digitalization as businesses began to rely more on technology to enhance their processes. The use of mobile devices and cloud computing services in the 2010s and 2020s to access information and applications at anytime, anywhere, and on any device (Berisha-Shaqiri, 2014).

Emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and IoT continue to transform industries and propel digital transformation. These technologies are empowering companies to enhance business processes, elevate customer experiences, and drive innovation. (Aldoseri et al., 2024). As DT evolves, technology is increasingly play a central role in shaping the future of business and society (Schallmo et al., 2018). DT is considered a strategic imperative for companies aiming to remain competitive and responsive to customers' and stakeholders' needs (Westerman et al., 2014).

The effect of digital transformation on university libraries has been profound. One major

trend is the shift towards digital collections and resources as libraries increasingly acquire e-books, electronic journals and other electronic materials. This has led to a focus on digital preservation and management, which strives to ensure that digital materials remain accessible and usable over time. DT has also affected library users. With the rise of digital resources, users now have access to a wider range of materials and can conveniently retrieve them remotely from anywhere with internet access (Darko Adjei & King, 2024; Kari, 2020). Digital Transformation in university libraries of Pakistan refers to the process of employing digital technology to improve services, collections, and user experience. This involves the digitization of library materials, automation of library processes, and the development of digital tools. University libraries in Pakistan need to remain relevant to their users by ensuring that services offered are convenient and personalized (Ameen & Rafiq, 2009; Aslam et al., 2025; Jabeen et al., 2024).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Keeping in view the digital transformation benefits for digital access to the users many university libraries are struggling to keep up with the rapidly evolving digital landscape. So there is a need to study the prospects of digital transformation in university libraries of Punjab, Pakistan. The study is being conducting on librarians working in Higher Education Commission (HEC) Degree Awarding Institutes (DAIs) Punjab, Pakistan. This study explain that what resources were digitized during the digital transformation, what challenges were faced. This study also helps those libraries who are interested in adoption of digitization and know in advance what difficulties was faced.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Following research questions meet the need of the study:

1. To find out the resources that are being digitized.
2. To explore the impact of digital transformation in university libraries of Punjab.
3. To discover the challenges of digital transformation in university libraries of Punjab.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research queries thoroughly examined in the paper:

RQ1. What types of resources are being digitized?

RQ2. What is the impact of digital transformation on university library?

RQ3. What kinds of challenges are faced during the implementation?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital transformation involves user interactions in order to drive innovation, improve efficiency, create new opportunities for growth and competitiveness (Verhoef et al., 2021). The goal of digital transformation in libraries is to improve the services and resources offered to users and enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of library operations (Deja, 2021). The shift from a "library for books" to a "library for people" is the subject of discussion. As a result, modern libraries place a strong emphasis on digital collections, and librarians have been developing skills related to digital curation (Khrushch et al., 2021).

Jaguszewski (2013) noted that DT can potentially improve access to information, enhance cooperation and communication and optimize workflows in libraries. The importance of libraries is becoming platforms for digital services rather than simply repositories for information. Consider incorporating services like online learning, social networking, and e-commerce into library operations. This way, libraries will be able to

better meet the needs of their users and stay relevant in the modern world (Arif & Mahmood, 2012; Baker, 2017).

Sandhu (2018) analyzed current trends and future perspectives in DT in academic libraries. They identified several key strategies, such as developing staff digital skills, embedding digital services in the library strategy and focusing on user-centred design. Singh (2019) identified several practices that need to be considered for successful digital transformation in university libraries, including the employee's approach, stakeholders' engagement, and constant evaluation of the digital services.

Despite the many benefits of DT libraries also face a number of challenges. They have to struggle with such problems as privacy and security as well as ensure that all people can access the resources irrespective of their digital literacy (Onunka et al., 2023). The challenges of digital transformation in Higher Education Institutions and identified issues such as inadequate funding, lack of digital skills among staff and resistance to change as major obstacles to DT (Rodrigues, 2017).

Libraries face some challenges when implementing DT. One of the primary issues is the employees' reluctance toward transformation (Rahman et al., 2024). Another challenge lies in the compatibility of outdated systems and infrastructure. The library infrastructure might be outdated and incapable of supporting digital replacements. Upgrading systems is tough because it is hard to transfer data from outdated storages to new ones without losing sensitive information. The implementation process may be inhibited by the budget restrictions and lack of professional digital knowhow. Libraries must also grapple with the intricate copyright and licensing ramifications of digitizing materials. Data security and privacy are critical, so libraries need to implement adequate measures and comply with respective regulations (Hamad et al., 2023; Meesad & Mingkhwan, 2024; Tedd & Large, 2005).

In one study found that some libraries had implemented digital technologies such as online catalogs and databases and many were still dependent on traditional methods of information storage and retrieval. The study also noted that lack of funding and technical expertise were major obstacles to digital transformation in Pakistani libraries (Rafiq et al, 2011). Rafiq and Ameen (2016) analyzed in "Towards a Digitization Framework: Pakistani Perspective". They found that digital resources were becoming increasingly available. There were challenges in terms of providing access to users due to issues such as lack of funding and resources as well as a lack of awareness among the public about the services offered by libraries.

As can be seen previously very few researches have been done to investigate the DT in libraries. Several of the studies only looked just particular research services. The literature shows the gap on the said field and it has drawn attention to the need for more thorough investigation regarding the challenges, opportunities, and outcomes of these transformations in this specific cultural and organizational setting.

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for this study was involved a quantitative approach. The investigator collected data through a structured questionnaire that was prepared on Google Forms and sent the link through email. Calls were placed to them before sending the questionnaire and sixty-nine librarians gave consent on mobile to fill out the questionnaire.

After receiving data, it was analyzed through SPSS and used descriptive statistics for the interpretation of the results. The questionnaire developed by consulted relevant literature and identified the themes as per the objectives of the current study. The population of interest was librarians working in university libraries of Punjab, who possess in-depth knowledge and expertise in digital technologies and their implementation in library settings. There are ninety-four (94) chartered universities in Punjab and librarians from sixty-nine (69) chartered universities participated in this study. The list of participating universities is provided in Appendix B. Purposive sampling was employed to select participants who were involved in digital resource services. The research methodology seeks to provide valuable insights into the challenges, outcomes, and recommendations regarding digital transformation efforts in Pakistani university libraries from the viewpoint of digital experts.

DATA ANALYSIS

This study was undertaken to find out the digital transformation in university libraries of Pakistan. In this section, the analysis of received data has been discussed.

Demographic Information

The findings (Table 1) revealed that all respondents are male 54(78.3%), and possessed the designation of librarian 56(81.2%) and assistant librarian 11(15.9%). The results demonstrated that majority of the respondents 59(66.7%) did MLIS/MLS, M.Phil 9(13.1%) and only one (1.4%) respondent have done PhD degree in library and information sciences. The results showed that majority of the respondents 51(73.9%) were working from 1 to 10 years in the field of library and information sciences.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Sample (n=69)

Variables	Levels	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	54	78.3
	Female	15	21.7
Designation	Librarian	56	81.2
	Library Manager	2	2.9
	Assistant Librarian	11	15.9
Professional qualification	MLIS/MLS	59	85.5
	M.Phil	9	13.1
	PhD.	1	1.4
Professional experience	1-10	51	73.9
	11-20	18	26.1
	Above 20	0	0.0

Aspects of Digital Transformation

The respondents were asked that which is the importance of following aspects in your library's digital transformation. The findings listed in Table 2 showed that majority of the respondents responded that human resources 48(69.6%), technology 47(68.1%), and financial resources 42(60.9%) are the most important aspects for digital transformation. However, a large number of respondents replied that evaluation and maintenance 60(86.9%), operations 58(84.1%), library materials 55(79.7%), platforms 51(73.9%), strategy 47(68.1%) are also important aspects for digital transformation.

Table 2: Aspects of digital transformation in library (n=69)

Sr.#	Aspects	<u>Most Important</u>		<u>Important</u>		<u>Not Important</u>	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1	Human resources	48	69.6	21	30.4	0	0.0
2	Financial resources	42	60.9	27	39.1	0	0.0
3	Library material (e.g. books, etc.)	14	20.3	55	79.7	0	0.0
4	Strategy	22	31.9	47	68.1	0	0.0
5	Operations	11	15.9	58	84.1	0	0.0
6	Technology	47	68.1	22	31.9	0	0.0
7	Platforms	18	26.1	51	73.9	0	0.0
8	Evaluation and maintenance	9	13.1	60	86.9	0	0.0
9	Other (please specify):						

Types of Software

The respondents asked that which type of software you have installed for the management of digitized resources. The findings listed in Table 3 revealed that majority of the respondents 51(73.9%) are using customized free software while 10(14.5%) respondents are using free software. Moreover, 5(7.2%) respondents are using in-house software for the for the management of digitized resources.

Table 3: Type of software used in library (n=69)

Sr. #	Types of Software	Yes (%)	No (%)
1	In-house software	5(7.2%)	64(92.8%)
2	Commercial software	3(4.3%)	66(95.7%)
3	Free software (non-customizable)	10(14.5%)	59(85.5%)
4	Free software (customizable)	51(73.9%)	8(26.1%)

Types of Digitized Resources

The respondents were asked that what are the types of digitized resources in your library. Table 4 explains the results related to types of digitized resources. The findings revealed that majority of the respondents responded that their libraries have different types of digitized resources including e-journals 69(100%), e-newspapers 53(76.8%), e-books 49(71%), scanned theses/dissertations 41(59.4%), scanned books 36(52.2%), E-theses/dissertations 23(33.3%), and A-V materials 13(18.8%).

Table 4: Types of digitized resources in library (n=69)

Sr. #	Digitized resources	Yes (%)	No (%)
1	Scanned books	36(52.2%)	33(47.8%)
2	E-books (born digital)	49(71%)	20(29%)
3	Scanned journals	1(1.4%)	68(98.6%)
4	E-journals (born digital)	69(100%)	-
5	E-reports (born digital)	12(17.4%)	57(82.6%)
6	Scanned newspaper(S)	2(2.9%)	67(97.1%)
7	E-newspaper(s) (born digital)	53(76.8%)	16(23.2%)
8	Scanned theses/dissertations	41(59.4%)	28(40.6%)
9	E-theses/dissertations (born digital)	23(33.3%)	46(66.7%)
10	A-V materials	13(18.8%)	56(81.2%)

Digital Platforms Used in Library

The respondents asked about digital platforms were used in their library. The findings showed in Table 5. The results demonstrated that majority of the respondents are using integrated library system 69(100%), institutional repository 42(60.9%), and content management system 39(56.5%).

Table 5: Digital platforms used in library(n=69)

Sr. #	Digital platforms	Yes (%)	No (%)
1	Integrated Library System (ILS) (e.g. Koha).	69(100%)	-
2	Institutional Repository (IR) (e.g. Calibre)	42(60.9%)	27(39.1%)
3	Content Management System (CMS) (e.g. DSpace)	39(56.5%)	30(43.5%)
4	Learning Management System (LMS) (e.g. Moodle)	4(5.8%)	65(94.2%)
5	Mobile phone App(s)	17(24.6%)	52(75.4%)

Use of Hosting Service for Library

The respondents asked that where does your library host its data. The results are listed in Table. The outcomes revealed that respondents 54(78.3%) are using own servers for hosting services for their libraries. Respondents 15(21.7%) are using free cloud hosting service and no respondent was using paid cloud hosting service for their libraries.

Table 6: Use of hosting Service for library(n=69)

Sr. #	Hosting service for library	Yes (%)	No (%)
1	Free cloud hosting	15(21.7%)	54(78.3%)
2	Paid cloud hosting	-	69(100%)
3	Own server(s)	54(78.3%)	15(21.7%)

Use for Technologies for Services and Communication

The findings related to use of technologies for services and communication are listed in Table 7. The results showed that majority of the respondents are using university website 69(100%), library website 69(100%), internet 69(100%), HEC digital library 69(100%), social media 69(100%), links to other website(s) for free resources 69(100%), phone call 69(100%), email 69(100%), RSS feed 69(100%) for services and communication.

Table 7: Use of Technology for Services and Communication (n=69)

Sr. #	Media/Technology or Access Platform	Yes (%)	No (%)
1	University website	69(100%)	-
2	Library website	69(100%)	-
3	Internet (LAN)	69(100%)	-
4	Attached or embedded links at LMS	44(63.8%)	25(36.2%)
5	HEC digital library	69(100%)	-
6	VPN	44(63.8%)	25(36.2%)
7	WhatsApp, etc.	38(55.1%)	31(44.9%)
8	Mobile phone library app(s)	17(24.6%)	52(75.4%)
9	Social media site(s) (e.g. Facebook)	69(100%)	-
10	YouTube, etc.	-	69(100%)
11	TV	-	69(100%)
12	Radio	-	69(100%)
13	Links to other website(s) for free resources	69(100%)	-
14	Resource sharing with other libraries	35(50.7%)	34(49.3%)
15	Phone call	69(100%)	-
16	SMS	1(1.4%)	68(98.6%)
17	Email	69(100%)	-
18	RSS feed	69(100%)	-
19	Web form	11(15.9%)	58(84.1%)
20	Chat box at website	50(72.5%)	19(27.5%)
21	Digital FAQs	29(42%)	40(58%)
22	Non-digital media	-	69(100%)

Challenges in the Way of Digital Transformation

Table 8 listed results related to challenges in the way of digital transformation. The outcomes revealed that majority of the respondents are either strongly agreed or agreed that lack of technological infrastructure 60(87%), copyright/DRM and licensing issues 57(82.6%), user authentication issues 55(79.7%), resistance to change in staff 53(76.8%), lack of competent staff 48(69.6%), data security and privacy issues 41(59.4%), inadequate funding 37(53.6%) are the major challenges in the way of digital transformation.

Table 8: Challenges in the Way of Digital Transformation(n=69)

Sr.#	Challenges	<u>Strongly Agree</u>		<u>Agree</u>		<u>Not Agree</u>	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1	Inadequate funding	19	27.6	37	53.6	13	18.8
2	Lack of competent staff	48	69.6	0	0.0	21	30.4
3	Resistance to change in staff	53	76.8	0	0.0	16	23.2
4	Copyright/DRM and licensing issues	12	17.4	57	82.6	0	0.0
5	User authentication issues	9	13.1	55	79.7	5	7.2
7	Data security and privacy issues	16	23.2	41	59.4	12	17.4
8	Lack of technological	60	87.0	0	0.0	9	13.0

	infrastructure							
9	Lack of support from university's top management	23	33.3	0	0.0	46	66.7	
10	Irregular electricity supply	0	0.0	28	40.6	41	59.4	
11	Other (please specify)							

DISCUSSION

The DT is the process through which firms integrate technology into their operations to generate fundamental change. The DT increased efficiency, increased company agility, and ultimately, the creation of new value for workers, customers, and shareholders. Emerging technologies like artificial intelligence, blockchain, and IoT are transforming sectors and propelling digital transformation ahead (Gul & Bano, 2019). These technologies allow organizations to simplify processes, enhance interactions with consumers, and innovate in novel and interesting ways. As digital transformation progresses, it is obvious that technology play an increasingly important role in determining business and society's future (Schallmo et al., 2018).

This study aims to investigate the digital transformation in university libraries of Punjab. This study examines DT in sixty-nine university libraries of Punjab, Pakistan. This study found that the respondents agreed that human and financial resources, technology, library material, strategy, and operations are the important aspects of digital transformation. These are the essentials things that required starting the process of DT in any university library. This study discovered that most of the libraries were using customizable free software. The possible reason behind the use of customizable free software because it is easy to use.

In Pakistani university libraries, main library contents are consisted of books, print journals, e-journals, newspapers. Thus, the university libraries are digitizing these types of contents to provide the online digitized material with printed materials. The software using to store and disseminate these digitized materials is integrated and has the ability to provide platform to make the institute repository. The university libraries in Pakistan are using different kinds of technologies to transform the contents from print to digital including website, internet, and attached embedded links at LMS, HEC digital library, VPN, WhatsApp, and social media. The Pakistani university libraries are using these technologies because these are available and the library staff have the expertise to utilize these technologies for the purpose of digitize materials from printed contents.

Sixty-nine university libraries participated for this study which having the strong IT infrastructure and engaged with DT activities as compared to other university libraries in Pakistan. However, these university libraries are facing different kinds of challenges to digitize the printed resources. These challenges are inadequate funds, copyright, data security, and lack of competent staff, and staff un-willingness. The DT process required tools and competent staff to digitize the printed resources. Nevertheless, lack of funds is the always a major issue for under-developed country such as Pakistan. The university authorities paid concentration towards the development of libraries because HEC requirement. Most of the university authorities are not take interest to provide budget for the implementation advanced technologies. The second major issue is lack of competencies

and un-willingness in library staff. The university authorities should understand the importance of novel technologies enhance their library budget. Libraries should also integrate their curriculum with innovative technologies so that students can seek knowledge about new technologies and can implement it on workstation.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to investigate the digital transformation in university libraries of Punjab, Pakistan and study was involving a quantitative approach. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire. Sixty-nine university libraries participated for this study which have the strong IT infrastructure and engaged with DT activities as compared to other university libraries. This study found that the respondents agreed that human resource, financial resources, and technology are the most important aspects of digital transformation. The results discovered that most of the libraries are using customizable free software. The findings revealed that majority of the respondents responded that their libraries have different types of digitized resources including scanned books, e-books, e-journals, e-reports, e-newspapers, scanned theses/dissertations, and A-V materials. The majority of the respondents are using integrated library system, content management system, and institutional repository. All respondents are using own servers and having free cloud for hosting services for their libraries. The respondents are mostly using university website, library website, internet, HEC digital library, social media, and links to other website for free resources, phone call, email, and RSS feed for services and communication. This study highlight some key challenges such as copyright/DRM and licensing issues, inadequate funding, user authentication issues, data security and privacy issues.

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Appendix A

Questionnaire

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES OF PUNJAB, PAKISTAN

Questionnaire

I am a student of PhD, Department of Library and Information Sciences, Allama Iqbal Open University Islamabad. I am conducting research on “Digital Transformation in University Libraries of Punjab, Pakistan”. For this purpose, I need your valuable feedback. I ensure this information will only be used anonymously for research purpose.

Regards

Tahir Raza

1. Demographic Information:

1.1. Name of the University: _____

1.2. Designation: _____

1.3. Gender: _____

1.4. Professional qualification: _____

1.5. Professional experience in years: _____

2. Which is the importance of following aspects in your library’s digital transformation?

Sr.#	Aspects	Most Important	Important	Not Important
1	Human resources			
2	Financial resources			
3	Library material (e.g. books, etc.)			
4	Strategy			
5	Operations			
6	Technology			
7	Platforms			
8	Evaluation and maintenance			
9	Other (please specify):			N/A
10	Other (please specify):			

3. What type of software does your library use?

Sr.#	Types of Software	Yes	No
1	In-house software		
2	Commercial software		
3	Free software (non-customizable)		
4	Free software (customizable)		

4. What are the types of digitized resources in your library?

Sr.#	Resources	Yes	No
1	Scanned books		
2	E-books (born digital)		
3	Scanned journals		
4	E-journals (born digital)		
5	E-reports (born digital)		
6	Scanned newspaper(S)		
7	E-newspaper(s) (born digital)		
8	Scanned theses/dissertations		
9	E-theses/dissertations (born digital)		
10	A-V materials		
11	Other(s) (please specify) _____ _____		

5. What digital platforms are used in your library?

Sr.#	Platforms	Yes	No
1	Integrated Library System (ILS) (e.g. Koha)		
2	Institutional Repository (IR) (e.g. Calibre)		
3	Content Management System (CMS) (e.g. DSpace)		
4	Learning Management System (LMS) (e.g. Moodle)		
5	Mobile phone App(s)		
6	Other(s) (please specify) _____ _____		

6. Where does your library host its data?

Sr.#	Host	Yes	No
1	Free cloud hosting		
2	Paid cloud hosting		
3	Own server(s)		

7. What media/technology or access platform does your library use for services and communication?

Sr.#	Media/Technology or Access Platform	Yes	No
1	University website		
2	Library website		
3	Intranet (LAN)		
4	Attached or embedded links at LMS		
5	HEC digital library		
6	VPN		
7	WhatsApp, etc.		

8	Mobile phone library app(s)		
9	Social media site(s) (e.g. Facebook)		
10	YouTube, etc.		
11	TV		
12	Radio		
13	Links to other website(s) for free resources		
14	Resource sharing with other libraries		
15	Phone call		
16	SMS		
17	Email		
18	RSS feed		
19	Web form		
20	Chat box at website		
21	Digital FAQs		
22	Non-digital media		
23	Other(s) (please specify) ~~~~~ ~~~~~		

8. What are the challenges in the way of digital transformation?

Sr.#	Challenges	Most Important	Important	Not Important
1	Inadequate funding			
2	Lack of competent staff			
3	Resistance to change in staff			
4	Copyright/DRM and licensing issues			
5	User authentication issues			
7	Data security and privacy issues			
8	Lack of technological infrastructure			
9	Lack of support from university's top management			
10	Irregular electricity supply			
11	Other (please specify) ~~~~~			N/A
12	Other (please specify) ~~~~~			
13	Other (please specify) ~~~~~			
14	Other (please specify) ~~~~~			

9. Any other point not covered above.

Appendix B

List of Participating Universities of Punjab

Sr#	Name of University
1.	Bahauddin Zakariya University
2.	Cholistan University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Bahawalpur
3.	Faisalabad Medical University, Faisalabad
4.	Fatima Jinnah Women University, Rawalpindi
5.	GIFT University
6.	Government College for Women University, Sialkot
7.	Government College University, Lahore
8.	Imperial College of Business Studies
9.	Institute for Art and Culture
10.	Institute of Management Sciences
11.	Khawaja Freed University of Engineering & Information Technology, Rahim Yar Khan
12.	Lahore School of Economics
13.	Lahore University of Management Sciences
14.	Namal University, Mainwali
15.	National College of Business Administration & Economics
16.	National University of Medical Sciences
17.	Pir Mehr Ali Shah Arid Agriculture University
18.	Rashid Latif Khan University, Lahore
19.	Rawalpindi Women University, Rawalpindi
20.	The Superior University
21.	The Women University
22.	University of Agriculture
23.	University of Chakwal, Chakwal
24.	University of Child Health Sciences, Lahore
25.	University of Engineering & Technology
26.	University of Gujrat
27.	University of Home Economics, Lahore
28.	University of Lahore
29.	University of Management & Technology
30.	University of Narowal
31.	University of Sahiwal
32.	University of Sialkot, Sialkot
33.	University of the Punjab
34.	University of Wah
35.	Beaconhouse National University
36.	Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore
37.	Forman Christian College
38.	Government Sadiq College Women University

39.	Information Technology University of the Punjab
40.	Institute of Management and Applied Sciences, Khanewal
41.	Institute of Southern Punjab
42.	Islamia University Bahawalpur
43.	King Edward Medical University
44.	Lahore Garrison University
45.	Lahore Leads University
46.	Minhaj University Lahore
47.	Muhammad Nawaz Shareef University of Agriculture
48.	National College of Arts
49.	National Textile University
50.	Nur International University Lahore
51.	Pakistan Institute of Fashion & Design Lahore
52.	Punjab Tianjin University of Technology, Lahore
53.	Qarshi University Lahore
54.	Rawalpindi Medical University
55.	The University of Faisalabad
56.	Times Institute, Multan
57.	University of Central Punjab
58.	University of Chenab, Gujrat
59.	University of Education Lahore
60.	University of Engineering & Technology, Taxila
61.	University of Health Sciences Lahore
62.	University of Jhang
63.	University of Layyah
64.	University of Mianwali
65.	University of Okara
66.	University of Sargodha
67.	University of South Asia Lahore
68.	University of Veterinary & Animal Sciences Lahore
69.	Virtual University of Pakistan